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1. Abbreviations

H₂ - Hydrogen

DI - Direct Injection

PFI - Port Fuel Injection

DOHC - Double Overhead Camshaft

RPEMS: Rapid Prototype Engine Management System

EGR - Exhaust Gas Recirculation

UPV - Universitat Politècnica de València (Polytechnic University of Valencia)

2. Summary

This report outlines the main details of the Single Cylinder H₂ engine as it has been built and its main specifications. Furthermore, pictures of the engine being installed on the UPV testbed, proving that it is almost ready for testing, are shown in Chapter 3.

3. H₂ICE prototype technical specification

3.1 Technical specifications of the H₂ research engine

The 4-stroke single-cylinder H₂ engine is designed for research and development of different Injection systems (DI, PFI) and different combustion parameters and their influence on engine performance. The engine consists of the reinforced Basic Unit AVL Type 5300 "HEDE", a separate cylinder block and a specially prepared cylinder head which features tumble charge motion and is prepared for H₂ injection equipment, both for direct injection and port fuel injection in the intake manifold. The engine design concept is without oil and coolant pumps, which must be externally installed at the testbed.

Table 1: Overview of Single-Cylinder Engine Specification

Number of cylinders	1	
Cylinder bore	135 mm	
Stroke	150 mm	
Swept volume	2,15 L	
Combustion system	4-valve, 4-stroke engine	
Top work	Single-cylinder head / DOHC	
Oil pressure	Min. 4 bar high PFP load	
Fuel	Hydrogen	
Fuel system	Direct injection, Port fuel injection	
Engine management system	AVL RPEMS	
Idle speed	500 rpm	
Maximum speed	2000 rpm "high idle" 2320 rpm	AVL base engine 3000 rpm
Piston	Tumble and swirl piston	
Compression ratio ϵ	13:1, 12:1	
Injector type	Liebherr H2 DI & PFI	
Valves per cylinder	2 intake / 2 exhaust	

Liner type	Wet, top hung	
Engine rotation	Clockwise	View on front
Timing drive type	Gear drive / belt drive to camshafts	
Timing rotation	Clockwise	View on front
Mass balancer	1 st & 2 nd order	
Engine weight (approximately)	~ 1000kg	Without oil and coolant
Engine inertia	8,471 kgm ²	Including flywheel

For further engine details, including sensors, actuators, and measurement equipment, please refer to the report *D6.1 H2ICE prototype technical specification data and manual*.

3.2 Pictures of the Engine

The following pictures show the engine ready for commissioning on the UPV testbed.

Figure 1: Engine in UPV testbed ready for commissioning - front view

Figure 2: Engine in UPV testbed ready for commissioning - side view

Figure 3: Engine in UPV testbed ready for commissioning - rear view

As can be seen, the engine is already assembled and awaiting commissioning at the UPV testbed, which is ongoing as this report is being submitted.

The following steps of the commissioning will be:

- Finishing the mounting of the engine in the test cell.
- The installation of the EGR system.
- Connecting all the sensors in the test cell with their measurement devices.
- Connecting the exhaust measurement devices.
- Setting up the engine control system.
- Setting up the testbed automation system and hook up all measurement devices.

4. Conclusion

The report shows that the Single-cylinder engine has successfully been adapted for H₂ operation and is already at the UPV installations, on its testbed. The remaining engine commissioning tasks are taking place as this report is being written. The engine will be ready to start the experimental program as soon as the commissioning is finalized.